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D. Thomas: Translation Vibes and Obstacles

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If we could describe the figure of Thomas in a few words, it would probably be the following phrases: “a man who lives according to the romantic canon”, “bohemian man”, “free spirit man” [3, p.168].

The biography of the Welsh-English poet is actually very difficult to write. Significant facts about his life can take only a few pages. Thomas’ real life consists of conversations in pubs, sometimes brawls and obscene antics. It would be unfair to remove these mythological aspects from his biography. In the existence of the poet, we cannot distinguish myth from truth. This feature was passed on to his works. Sometimes it is very difficult to determine what prevails in his poems – sincerity or imagination.

Some critics believe that Thomas’ literary legacy is very unequal. There are very few works left after him and only a third of his poems deserves the highest praise. Prose works in general remain invaluable in the author’s circles. However, in English-language literature D. Thomas is considered the most important poet of the XX century, the last legend of Romanticism, and his best poems continue to be quoted almost everywhere.

Leslie Norris who published a volume of D. Thomas’ prose [6] concludes his preface with the following words: “One of my acquaintances told me that his mother did not want to read Thomas because he was such a terrible person. When she was persuaded, she changed her mind and now convinced that he is a wonderful person. I agree with her.” [6]

M. Virozub, one of the researchers of the electronic magazine “Zhurnalnyy zal”, in his review “Great and complex D. Thomas” notes that from the perspective of translation work, this author is difficult to present to Russian-speaking readers as he really was. The fact is that Thomas’ poems have been translated by many and it is very difficult for a person who does not speak English to set priorities for himself.

In the 2015 edition of *The Great D. Thomas* which was reviewed by M. Virozub, the compiler collected many different translations of the author. Perhaps he wanted the reader to see different views on the work of the Welsh poet, to compare his thoughts with the thoughts and feelings of the translators. Sometimes we even have the opportunity to compare several translations of one verse. For example, it happened with the poem “And Death Shall Have no Dominion”. The book featured six translations of this work.

However, according to the author of the review, the compiler did not always choose the best translations of Thomas’ works. The author of the review reveals the features of the poet’s artistic thinking, which are embodied in the antithesis of “iambic blood – chemic blood”. “For example, in a case of the poem “Especially when the October wind” none of the translators seemed

to understand it correctly. The meaning is that the poet's blood is "iambic blood". It is full of images and life around it, and the poet uses his blood to paint the image of "Her" – the love of his life. But in the end the poet says that he gave everything, and now "chemic blood" flows. This is a key and untranslated image: one of the translators leaves this phrase as it is, and then it has no meaning, and someone misses this detail at all. The phrase means that the poet is left with chemically pure blood, that is, he is completely devastated! As a result, one of the brightest poems becomes ordinary and passable." [4] The researcher emphasizes specific images, metaphors, word usages in the poet's poems. The translator simply has no right to ignore all this, because it is an integral part and essence of the poetic world of D. Thomas.

Another translator of Thomas A. Shtipel who studied at our university in his youth (although at the Faculty of Physics) [2], wrote his review of the Welsh poet's work – "My hero in his hand exposes the nerve" in the electronic version of the magazine "Novyy mir", 2010. Our translator accidentally came across the work of Thomas. Turning the pages of a collection of American and English poetry, his attention was drawn to three short poems by Thomas, which A. Shtipel was reluctant to try to translate. He enrolled in the Library of Foreign Literature and transcribed the poet's poems in his own notebook. He later came across a book of translations by four English poets, including Thomas: "I will not say anything bad about Thomas' translations of this book, it would be somehow incorrect, but I will not say anything good either. Exquisite phonetic drawing of D. Thomas' poems puts the translator in front of almost insurmountable difficulties" [2].

Frequently in the works of D. Thomas there are memories of childhood in the small town of Swansea where he lived for many years. Both in prose works and sometimes in verse, his "characters are strange, lonely, naive, senseless creatures, they invent their own world, preserve their dreams and dear memories" [1]. It is through these descriptions that we can hear the Welshman's soul, feel his childlike spontaneity and appreciate his prose and poetry.

The poet regarded the word as a miracle. His work is filled with Welsh nature and Celtic folklore. In his essay, Thomas said: "To be a poet, the poet is given the shortest time of his life and his responsibilities include knowing and experiencing everything that happens in the world and in his soul, and then poetry will be an attempt to discover the peaks of wisdom, found by a man on this unparalleled, and since 1946 for sure, crazy Earth" [5].

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